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**PREVALENCE OF ACUTE PHARYNGITIS
AMONG THE PATIENTS PRESENTING IN
OUTDOOR DEPARTMENT**

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ABSTRACT:

Pharyngitis is inflammation of the back of the throat, known as the pharynx. It typically results in a sore throat and fever. Other symptoms may include a runny nose, cough, headache, difficulty swallowing, swollen lymph nodes, and a hoarse voice. This cross-sectional study was conducted among the patients presenting in the medical outdoor department of different hospitals. Name, age, gender and history and duration of acute pharyngitis were noted on a predefined proforma. All the data was entered and analyzed with SPSS Ver. 23.0. A total of 100 patients presenting in outdoor were included in this study i.e., 50 males (50%) and 50 females (50%). The mean age of the patients was 33.23 ± 3.67 years. Out of 100 patients, sixteen patients presented with acute pharyngitis and maximum duration was 2 months and the minimum was 1 week.

Keyword: Acute Pharyngitis

INTRODUCTION:

Pharyngitis is inflammation of the back of the throat, known as the pharynx. It typically results in a sore throat and fever. Other symptoms may include a runny nose, cough, headache, difficulty swallowing, swollen lymph nodes, and a hoarse voice. Symptoms usually last 3–5 days. Complications can include sinusitis and acute otitis media. Pharyngitis is a type of upper respiratory tract infection. Most cases are caused by a viral infection. Strep throat, a bacterial infection, is the cause in about 25% of children and 10% of adults. Uncommon causes include other bacteria such as gonorrhea, fungus, irritants such as smoke, allergies, and gastroesophageal reflux disease. Specific testing is not recommended in people who have clear symptoms of a viral infection, such as a cold. Otherwise, a rapid antigen detection test (RADT) or throat swab is recommended. Other conditions that can produce similar symptoms include epiglottitis, thyroiditis, retropharyngeal abscess, and occasionally heart disease.

NSAIDs, such as ibuprofen, can be used to help with the pain. Numbing medication, such as topical lidocaine, may also help. Strep throat is typically treated with antibiotics, such as either penicillin or amoxicillin. If steroids are useful in acute pharyngitis, other than possibly in severe cases, is unclear but a recent (2020) review found that when used in combination with antibiotics they moderately improved pain and the likelihood of resolution.

About 7.5% of people have a sore throat in any 3-month period. Two or three episodes in a year are not uncommon. This resulted in 15 million physician visits in the United States in 2007. Pharyngitis is the most common cause of a sore throat. The word comes from the Greek word pharynx meaning "throat" and the suffix -itis meaning "inflammation". Pharyngitis is a type of inflammation caused by an upper respiratory tract infection. It may be classified as acute or chronic. Acute pharyngitis may be catarrhal, purulent, or ulcerative, depending on the causative agent and the immune capacity of the affected individual. Chronic pharyngitis may be catarrhal, hypertrophic, or atrophic.

Tonsillitis is a subtype of pharyngitis. If the inflammation includes both the tonsils and other parts of the throat, it may be called pharyngotonsillitis or tonsillopharyngitis. Another subclassification is nasopharyngitis (1-3).

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This cross-sectional study was conducted among the patients presenting in the medical outdoor department of different hospitals. Name, age, gender and history and duration of acute pharyngitis were noted on a predefined proforma. All the data was entered and analyzed with SPSS Ver. 23.0. The quantitative variables were presented as mean and standard deviation. The qualitative variables were presented as frequency and percentages.

RESULTS:

A total of 100 patients presenting in outdoor were included in this study i.e., 50 males (50%) and 50 females (50%). The mean age of the patients was 33.23 ± 3.67 years. Out of 100 patients, sixteen patients presented with acute pharyngitis and maximum duration was 2 months and the minimum was 1 week.

DISCUSSION:

Differentiating a viral and a bacterial cause of a sore throat based on symptoms alone is difficult. Thus, a throat swab often is done to rule out a bacterial cause. The modified Centor criteria may be used to determine the management of people with pharyngitis. Based on five clinical criteria, it indicates the probability of a streptococcal infection. One point is given for each of the criteria i.e. absence of a cough, swollen and tender cervical lymph nodes, temperature more than $38.0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ ($100.4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{F}$), tonsillar exudate or swelling and age less than 15 (a point is subtracted if age is more than 44)

The Infectious Disease Society of America recommends against empirical treatment and considers antibiotics only appropriate following positive testing. Testing is not needed in children under three, as both group A strep

and rheumatic fever are rare, except if they have a sibling with the disease. Pain medication, such as NSAIDs and acetaminophen (paracetamol), can help reduce the pain associated with a sore throat. Viscous lidocaine relieves pain by numbing the mucous membranes. Antibiotics are useful if a bacterial infection is the cause of the sore throat. For viral infections, antibiotics have no effect. In the United States, they are used in 25% of people before a bacterial infection has been detected. Oral analgesic solutions, the active ingredient is usually phenol, but also less commonly benzocaine, cetylpyridinium chloride, and/or menthol. Chloraseptic and Cepacol are two examples of brands of these kinds of analgesics (4-6).

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